

Report on ‘Next Generation Ocean Observing: Biogeochemical Sensors on Transport Mooring Arrays’ Workshop, February 2026, Edinburgh, UK

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Report on Workshop on ‘Next Generation Ocean Observing: Biogeochemical Sensors on Transport Mooring Arrays’ February 2026, Edinburgh, UK

1 Introduction

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is a central element of the climate system, carrying heat, freshwater, and mass across the basin and shaping the large-scale density structure of the ocean. Over the past two decades, sustained mooring arrays such as the RAPID-MOCHA-WBTS array at 26°N (e.g., Johns et al., 2011; McCarthy et al., 2015), OSNAP across the subpolar gyre (Lozier et al., 2019; Li et al., 2017), and gateway arrays at Davis Strait and Fram Strait (Curry et al., 2014; de Steur et al., 2009) have enabled a step-change in our understanding of large-scale circulation and its dynamics. These arrays have documented multi-year fluctuations in overturning strength (Smeed et al., 2018; Fu et al., 2025), revealed abrupt reorganisations of boundary current pathways (e.g., Holliday et al., 2020), and continue to provide continuous estimates of meridional heat and freshwater transports that serve as essential benchmarks for evaluating and validating models and reanalyses (e.g. Danabasoglu et al., 2026).

Although these observing systems were established to quantify the physical circulation, the AMOC also exerts a profound influence on the ocean’s biogeochemical and ecological state. It is widely recognised as the dominant mechanism behind the North Atlantic’s disproportionate role in absorbing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and storing it at depth on climatically-important timescales (e.g., Pérez et al., 2024; Brown et al., 2021). It is also the overturning circulation that ultimately ventilates the deep ocean (Rhein et al., 2017), redistributes oxygen and nutrients (Koelling et al., 2025; Williams et al., 2026), and transports anthropogenic carbon both into high latitude basins and to depth where it contributes to rapid acidification (Yasunaka et al., 2023; Pérez et al., 2018). Many of the questions now facing the biogeochemical and biological research communities (including how carbon uptake will evolve, how oxygen supply to the deep ocean is maintained, and how nutrient pathways support subpolar ecosystems) are tightly coupled to AMOC variability and long-term change. An observing system capable of resolving both the physical transports and the biogeochemical fields they carry could therefore unlock new understanding of both how circulation variability impacts the carbon, nutrient and biological systems of the North Atlantic, but also act as a monitoring system for anthropogenic climate change signals being propagated into the ocean interior (Tjiputra et al., 2023).

Over the last two decades, the technical capabilities of autonomous sensing systems for biogeochemical parameters have developed enormously (Wang et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2023). Although not yet at the level of stability, robustness and measurement frequency capabilities (or price-points) of more common physical characteristics like temperature, salinity, pressure and velocity, continued new developments are fast realising significant advances (Briciu-Burghina et al., 2023). Sensors for oxygen (Garçon et al., 2026), inorganic carbon (pH and pCO₂) (e.g. Hammermeister et al., 2025; Steinhoff et al., 2025), inorganic nutrients (Johnson et al., 2002; Cao et al., 2022), and autonomous water samplers have all advanced to the point where they can be deployed on moorings with sampling frequencies and accuracies that complement physical measurements. This rapid evolution means that opportunities to integrate biogeochemical observations into existing transport arrays are expanding quickly, offering the

potential to observe the coupled physical–biogeochemical system with a continuity that has not previously been possible. First steps have been taken at several arrays in adding BGC capabilities: at RAPID (Brown et al., 2021), at the Eastern boundary of OSNAP (Johnson et al., 2024), at western OSNAP moorings as part of the GOHSNAP project (Atamanchuk et al., 2021) and at Arctic Gateways (e.g. von Appen et al., 2021). Collectively these efforts demonstrate the feasibility and scientific value of integrating biogeochemical sensors onto moorings and show a clear direction of travel for fully equipping AMOC mooring arrays with BGC-relevant instrumentation.

In February 2026, we organised a [workshop](#) in Edinburgh, Scotland, for stakeholders from the broader marine science community to explore how such integration might be achieved. Bringing together physical oceanographers, marine biogeochemists, and sensor engineers, the meeting specifically focused on (i) introducing the scientific value of co-located measurements, (ii) discussing the technical and operational considerations of deploying biogeochemical sensors on transport moorings, (iii) the organisational structures and logistical considerations needed to support a more integrated Atlantic observing system and (iv) the challenges and opportunities that would benefit from the different communities working together. The discussions were framed by a shared recognition that the AMOC mooring arrays have become indispensable components of the global observing system, and that enhancing them with biogeochemical capability could unlock new scientific insight. Here, we summarise the outcomes of this workshop.

2 The scientific case for co-located physical and biogeochemical measurements

A consistent theme was that the AMOC's role in shaping the ocean's biogeochemical environment should no longer be a secondary consideration. A number of urgent questions about the Atlantic – from its continued capacity to absorb and store anthropogenic carbon to the future resilience of high-latitude ecosystems - depend on a keen understanding of how physical circulation interacts with chemical and biological processes. Examples were presented during the meeting that illustrated how much can be gained when these processes are observed together.

2.1 Anthropogenic carbon transports

One area where this integration has already proved transformative is the study of anthropogenic carbon transports. At subtropical latitudes, the high-resolution measurements from RAPID, combined with long-term historical BGC hydrographic observations, have shown that the overturning circulation is the primary mechanism controlling both the magnitude and variability northward anthropogenic carbon transport (Brown et al., 2021). Extending this calculation methodology to the North Atlantic subpolar gyre, preliminary analyses suggested a more complex structure than in the subtropics. Boundary-current pathways appear to play a larger role in the west, while overturning dominates in the east, and AMOC variability accounts for only a modest fraction of the overall anthropogenic carbon transport signal. Taken together, these emerging findings illustrate that integrating biogeochemical and physical measurements can reveal a more nuanced picture of how anthropogenic carbon is redistributed between the subtropics, subpolar gyre, and into the Arctic. Workshop discussions emphasised that carbon transport is not simply a passive reflection of circulation: as anthropogenic CO₂ continues to accumulate in the atmosphere, the vertical and horizontal gradients that drive the carbon transports are themselves changing. This changing background state means that the relationship between physical and biogeochemical fields is dynamic, and that integrated observing approaches are essential for tracking how the ocean's carbon uptake responds to ongoing climate forcing.

2.2 Oxygen ventilation and budgets

New oxygen observations from the OSNAP moorings in the Labrador Sea demonstrated the capability to capture the full seasonal cycle of deep convection and the subsequent export of oxygen-rich Labrador Sea Water into the boundary currents (Koelling et al., 2022). These measurements provide a detailed view of how ventilation signals are formed and transmitted, and allow their downstream evolution to be traced as they spread through the subpolar gyre. Further analyses using OSNAP data revealed a broader pattern of progressive oxygenation across the subpolar North Atlantic (Koelling et al., 2025). Combining the moored sensor observations with estimates of air–sea oxygen fluxes from autonomous profiling floats, has, for the first time, enabled the potential to close the oxygen budget of the subpolar gyre, a long-standing challenge that can only be addressed when physical and biogeochemical measurements are co-located. Workshop discussions highlighted how this integrated approach makes it possible to follow ventilation signals from their source regions into the ocean interior and to quantify how they are modified by mixing, stratification, and circulation. Participants also emphasised that oxygen is a particularly sensitive indicator of the coupled physical–biological system. Variations in ventilation, stratification, and productivity all leave distinct signatures in oxygen fields, making it a powerful diagnostic of the interplay between circulation, air–sea interaction and ecosystem functioning. Several speakers described oxygen as a “gateway variable” for biogeochemical observing — a measurement that delivers immediate scientific value while also supporting more complex budget analyses and the interpretation of other tracers. This opinion comes through a number of factors: the behaviour of the oxygen optode sensor is well-characterised (methodology of data processing and quality control of sensor outputs is now quite mature (Miller et al., 2024)); it is far more financially attainable / budget-friendly than other BGC parameters; although its calibration relies on wet chemistry discrete measurements (Winkler titrations) that must take place post-deployment and pre-recovery on board ship, this method is straightforward and relatively inexpensive to set up.

2.3 Biological carbon pump sensitivity

Work interrogating biological carbon pump sensitivity to circulation variability focused on continuous mooring-based observations from Fram Strait, which provided some of the first high-frequency time-series of inorganic nutrients and $p\text{CO}_2/\text{pH}$ alongside physical measurements (von Appen et al., 2021). These sustained observations revealed how sea-ice–derived meltwater stratification interacts with the biological carbon pump and modulates the depth and efficiency of carbon export. Years with strong meltwater export were seen to trap primary production in a shallow surface layer, limiting downward carbon flux, whereas weaker export allowed deeper winter mixing and more efficient transfer of organic carbon to depth. This work was only possible because the long-term, co-located physical and biogeochemical measurements could resolve the pathways through which freshwater variability (with strong links to AMOC-related circulation change) propagated into ecosystem functioning and carbon sequestration. Workshop discussions emphasised that similar sensitivities are likely to operate throughout the subpolar gyre; variability in winter mixing, eddy activity, and boundary-current structure all influence the vertical distribution of production and the fate of exported carbon, yet these processes are rarely observed with continuity. Participants noted that integrating biogeochemical sensors into transport arrays would allow these mechanisms to be monitored in real time and at basin scale, providing a foundation for understanding how the biological carbon pump responds to climate-driven changes in circulation and stratification.

2.4 Nutrient and carbon transports in the subpolar gyre

Recent analyses along the eastern boundary of the subpolar gyre were presented, where sustained observations have revealed that biogeochemical fluxes possess their own vertical structure, often distinct from that of the underlying volume transport (Johnson et al., 2024). In this region, the depths of maximum nitrate or phosphate transport can lie hundreds of metres below the depth of maximum velocity, reflecting the combined influence of vertical concentration gradients and the shear structure of the flow. On interannual timescales, variability in these biogeochemical transports is dominated by circulation changes, whereas on decadal timescales shifts in water-mass composition and background nutrient concentrations become increasingly important. Workshop discussions underscored that resolving these patterns requires sustained biogeochemical measurements co-located with physical transport arrays. Participants noted that integrating biogeochemical sensors into boundary-current and overturning-array moorings would allow the vertical structure of nutrient and carbon fluxes to be monitored continuously, providing a means to track how circulation variability, water-mass shifts, and climate-driven stratification changes propagate into nutrient supply and high-latitude ecosystem functioning.

Across these examples, the workshop highlighted how a wide range of biogeochemical and biological questions have started to be addressed by harnessing the long-term records emerging from existing mooring arrays and transport systems. Studies of anthropogenic carbon transport, oxygen ventilation and budgets, biological carbon pump sensitivity, and nutrient fluxes all demonstrate the scientific value unlocked when biogeochemical measurements are embedded within established physical observing infrastructures. Yet participants also noted that these successes represent only a fraction of what could be achieved. The existing arrays provide a powerful foundation, but fully exploiting their potential requires careful consideration of sensor capabilities, calibration strategies, deployment logistics, and data integration. These issues formed the focus of the subsequent workshop discussions.

3 Technical and operational realities of BGC-enabled moorings

The workshop's second theme focused on the practicalities of deploying biogeochemical sensors on moorings designed primarily for physical measurements. These discussions drew heavily on the operational experience of RAPID, OSNAP, OOI, Davis Strait, and Fram Strait, programmes that have collectively deployed hundreds of moorings over the past two decades and now provide a substantial foundation for new observations.

3.1 Sensor capabilities and performance

Discussions of sensor capabilities and performance emphasised that several considerations apply across all biogeochemical sensors, regardless of platform or measurement type. Power consumption and battery capacity remain fundamental constraints, shaping both sampling frequency and deployment duration. Response time determines the nature of a BGC sensor deployment, influencing whether an instrument is suitable for profiling, fixed-point sampling, or only slow-varying signals. Platform compatibility, including sensitivity to tilt, vibration, and mooring motion, also affects data quality and is a critical consideration when integrating sensors into moorings. It was stressed that accuracy and precision cannot be assessed from sensor output alone: all BGC sensors require coincident discrete measurements for calibration and validation, except in the rare cases where instruments carry their own internal standards. Even then, discrete samples remain essential, and their subsequent quality (and by extension the quality of the sensor outputs) depends on sampling technique, collection vessel,

preservation method (e.g. poisoning, freezing, refrigeration), and storage duration. Finally, samples must be analysed through certifiable laboratory analyses, which requires the infrastructure, specialised personnel, and instrumentation to support them.

Building on these general principles, the workshop examined the specific capabilities of lab-on-chip systems, which have advanced rapidly in recent years and are now able to provide high-frequency measurements of nitrate, phosphate, silicate, pH, and total alkalinity with precision approaching that of ship-based analyses. However, their operation introduces additional constraints: because chemical reagents are consumed during analysis, both reagent volume and waste-collection capacity must be considered, as these limit the total number of measurements. The chemical stability of reagents and standards - potentially affected by temperature or light - influences long-term performance, and power requirements must again be balanced against deployment duration. Participants noted that these limitations are easing as designs evolve and mature, but careful planning remains essential to ensure reliable operation over multi-month or multi-year deployments.

3.2 Engineering constraints

Discussions of engineering constraints highlighted that integrating biogeochemical sensors into moorings designed primarily for physical measurements introduces a series of practical challenges. Sampling schedule and sensor power consumption must be balanced with available battery storage – the latter can have knock-on effects on instrument dimensions and weight. Larger instruments add weight and drag that require careful attention to mooring design, buoyancy distribution, and deck handling. It was noted that transport mooring arrays have been optimised over many years to maximise reliability with minimal redundancy; participants stressed that adding complex biogeochemical packages should never compromise the stability or integrity of core transport measurements.

It was highlighted that many existing arrays rely on taut line moorings with limited space for additional instrumentation. Incorporating biogeochemical sensors may therefore require redesigning buoyancy packages, adjusting line lengths, or modifying anchor weights. These changes can have cascading effects on mooring dynamics, particularly in regions with strong currents, steep topography, or high drag environments. Several speakers emphasised that new configurations should be tested in controlled settings or through modelling before being deployed in the field.

Failures were acknowledged as inevitable: flooded sensor housings, exhaustion of batteries, reagent depletion, biofouling, and mechanical damage all occur even in well-designed systems. These risks must be anticipated in cruise planning, budgets, and data analysis workflows. Participants also noted that engineering constraints extend beyond the moorings themselves: deck space, winch capacity, and safe handling procedures can limit the number and type of biogeochemical sensors that can be deployed at a given location or on a given ship/cruise. As a result, successful integration requires close coordination between engineers, mooring technicians, biogeochemists, and physical oceanographers to ensure that new instrumentation can be accommodated without compromising operational safety or the reliability of long-standing transport measurements.

3.3 Calibration and drift correction

Calibration and drift correction emerged as critical issues. It was underscored that high quality biogeochemical observations depend as much on calibration strategy as on sensor technology with all BGC sensors exhibiting some combination of drift, offset, pressure dependence, and none could be validated from sensor output alone. Again, it was emphasised that coincident discrete samples remain

essential for establishing accuracy, correcting drift, and quantifying long term stability. For those instruments with internal calibration standards, discrete validation samples remain essential for isolating the effects of external biofouling on sensor outputs.

Different sensor types exhibit characteristic drift behaviours. Optical oxygen sensors show both reversible pressure related drift and irreversible foil degradation, requiring a combination of drift models and discrete Winkler titrations (Miller et al., 2024). Nitrate sensors require accurate salinity for bromide correction and typically show linear drift over time, although they can also exhibit step-changes in response. Subsurface pCO₂ sensors require sensor specific processing and careful validation against discrete DIC and total alkalinity samples. Across all platforms, calibration must be planned for throughout the deployment cycle rather than treated as a single, factory-based activity.

The workshop also highlighted the logistical dimension of calibration. As mentioned, collecting sufficient discrete samples requires ship time, laboratory capacity, and trained personnel, and ensuring consistency across different arrays will require coordination among operators, biogeochemists, and funding agencies. Several speakers noted that shared calibration protocols (including standardised sampling procedures, preservation methods, and analytical workflows) would help streamline this process and improve data consistency across programmes.

3.4 Data processing and delivery

Transport arrays such as RAPID and OSNAP have developed robust data pipelines over many years, with established version control, transparent documentation, and open-source processing frameworks. Integrating biogeochemical measurements into these pipelines will require adapting those processes to accommodate new variables, metadata standards, and quality control procedures. For biogeochemical sensor measurements, the largest delays between data acquisition and public release arises from the lengthy calibration, drift correction, and quality control steps required for reliable datasets. Participants noted that achieving reliable, traceable BGC data requires sustained investment in technical staff, data managers, and analytical capacity, and that these needs are often underestimated when new sensors are added to existing mooring programmes. As well as a technical task it is also an organisational one: data workflows, responsibilities, and timelines will need to evolve as BGC measurements become a routine component of mooring operations. As part of this the importance was stressed of delivering BGC data in formats that meet FAIR principles and are interoperable with other observing systems (Tanhua et al., 2021). This includes consistent metadata, clear documentation of calibration procedures, and transparent reporting of uncertainties. As with the process of calibration itself, achieving this consistency will require coordination across arrays, shared protocols, and long-term support for the personnel who maintain and curate these datasets.

3.5 Summary

Taken together, the discussions of sensor capabilities, engineering constraints, calibration requirements, and data workflows make clear that the technical and operational realities of integrating biogeochemical sensors into transport mooring arrays are challenging but achievable. The workshop highlighted the expertise that already exists, and how successful deployments depend on understanding sensor limitations, planning for power, reagents, and drift, and ensuring rigorous calibration through high quality discrete samples. Equally important to consider are the engineering adaptations required to integrate new instruments into long standing mooring designs, and the data processing capacity needed to deliver calibrated, traceable BGC records. It was emphasised that while these are not trivial undertakings, they are certainly not prohibitive: the experience gained across RAPID-MOCHA-WBTS,

OSNAP, OOI, Davis Strait, and Fram Strait demonstrates that BGC sensors can be incorporated reliably when technical, logistical, and data considerations are addressed from the outset. These operational insights formed the foundation for the workshop's subsequent discussions on the broader strategic, organisational, and funding considerations required to expand the integration of biogeochemistry across the AMOC observing system.

4 Working with existing transport mooring arrays

A recurring theme in discussions of working with existing transport arrays was the recognition that boundary and section arrays set up to monitor the AMOC represent some of the most stable, long running, and operationally mature ocean observing infrastructures in the world. Their continuity, logistical support, and established data pipelines make them natural platforms for expanding biogeochemical observing. However, at the same time it was reiterated that effective engagement with these arrays and the people who look after them requires a clear understanding of the functional realities and constraints within which they operate.

4.1 Logistical constraints

Discussions of logistical constraints first focused on the fact that transport arrays operate under tight and often inflexible schedules. Cruise plans are typically fixed years in advance, and many arrays require permits from multiple national authorities that need securing well ahead of time. For RAPID-MOCHA-WBTS, work in the Florida Straits and in coastal waters depends on long standing agreements with the Bahamas, while OSNAP deployments must navigate the permitting frameworks of Canada, Greenland, Iceland, and the UK. These requirements impose long lead times of often 6–12 months (or more) for any proposed addition of instrumentation or new sensing technologies. It was emphasised that these constraints are not simply bureaucratic hurdles to navigate but reflect the complexity of operating across multiple jurisdictions, each with its own regulatory requirements. Ensuring compliance requires careful planning and coordination among operators, funding agencies, and national authorities, and limits the feasibility of opportunistic or last-minute deployments.

4.2 Shipboard capacity

Space on board, both with relation to available berths and deck space / lab space was highlighted as a major limiting factor in expanding current mooring activities. Transport arrays turnaround cruises typically operate with lean teams and well-rehearsed deck operations optimised for reliability, efficiency and safety. Adding biogeochemical sensors, particularly larger packages such as sensor frames, or autonomous water samplers requires careful planning and interaction with deck staff to avoid compromising core transport measurements and the safe and timely deployment and recovery of core equipment. It was noted that designing biogeochemical packages that are compatible with existing mooring infrastructure is essential. In particular, focus should be applied to using modular frames that attach cleanly to mooring lines, integrating new sensors into existing buoyancy packages, or ensuring any extra instrumentation minimises additional drag. A close collaboration between sensor developers and mooring engineers was repeatedly highlighted as critical for ensuring safe and effective deployment.

4.3 Pathways to engage with the transport mooring array community

There was strong interest from across scientific backgrounds and mooring array operators to try to deepen collaboration with the biogeochemical community. Many arrays already host biogeochemical sensors of some fashion on a subset of their moorings, and where resources allowed, they were keen to expand these efforts and to welcome new collaborators. It was pointed out that transport mooring arrays offer a number of unique advantages to biogeochemical observing: fixed long term reference points, access to boundary currents that are difficult to sample with floats or gliders, and the temporal continuity needed to resolve interannual and decadal variability. There was an acknowledgement that the exact route/s to engage with the mooring array operators or new deployment opportunities are not always transparent to potential collaborators. Workshop participants identified a need for a concise, accessible resource that for each major array outlined points of contact, timelines for permits and diplomatic clearance applications, technical constraints, and expectations for data sharing and processing. Such a resource would lower the barrier to entry for biogeochemists and sensor developers and help ensure that new deployments align with array capabilities and scientific priorities as early as possible.

4.4 Linkages with BGC-Argo profiling floats and satellite observing

Aside from the strategy of using new biogeochemical measurements to undertake investigations into the dynamic relationships between biogeochemical fields and circulation variability, there was a discussion relating to linkages with BGC Argo and satellites, particularly relating to the potential for transport arrays to serve as calibration and validation sites for basin scale observing systems. Their fixed locations, high quality physical measurements, and capacity for co-located biogeochemical sensors could make them ideal for anchoring BGC-Argo and satellite products, in a complementary fashion to gold-standard shipboard measurements. It was thought that strengthening these linkages would benefit both communities: transport arrays would gain broader scientific relevance, while BGC Argo and satellite programmes would gain robust reference points for long term stability, error estimation and calibration/validation. A focus on high quality reference data for validating float-based estimates of oxygen, pH, and nitrate was postulated, to help constrain the vertical structure of biogeochemical fields that floats alone cannot fully resolve. Several speakers suggested that formal partnerships between transport arrays and BGC Argo programmes would help ensure these linkages are sustained over the long term.

5 Community priorities for a future observing system

The final session of the workshop brought participants together in smaller breakout groups to identify scientific opportunities, observational gaps, and research priorities for the coming decade. Despite the diversity of disciplinary backgrounds and regional interests, the groups converged on a set of shared themes that reflect the broader evolution of the AMOC observing community and its growing commitment to sustained biogeochemical measurements.

5.1 Oxygen as a core variable

One of the strongest points of consensus was the need to treat dissolved oxygen as a core variable on AMOC transport arrays. Oxygen plays a central role in ventilation, deoxygenation, and ecosystem

functioning, and its measurement is essential for closing oxygen budgets and understanding the biological carbon pump. As it integrates multiple processes that each leave distinct signatures in oxygen distributions, it is a powerful diagnostic variable for understanding the interplay between physical and biogeochemical processes. Oxygen sensors have now reached a level of maturity comparable to temperature and salinity sensors two decades ago: they are robust, low power, and capable of multi-year deployments at full ocean depth. Although requiring careful calibration and coincident discrete water calibration samples, this process is eminently achievable and relatively low cost. The workshop concluded that oxygen should no longer be considered an optional enhancement but become a standard component of AMOC observing, forming a foundation for more advanced biogeochemical integration.

5.2 Biogeochemical OSSEs

A second priority that was identified was the development of biogeochemical observing system simulation experiments (OSSEs). Physical OSSEs have been instrumental in designing the RAPID and OSNAP arrays and continue to be so, ensuring that the arrays as deployed best capture the magnitude and variability of AMOC, heat, and freshwater signals within technical constraints. Comparable experiments for biogeochemical variables however are largely non-existent. It was stressed that without biogeochemical focused OSSEs, there is a risk that future modifications to arrays, whether driven by funding constraints, ship availability, or evolving scientific priorities, could inadvertently degrade their ability to constrain biogeochemical transports and budgets and bridge key BGC knowledge gaps. Developing such OSSEs was identified as a high priority for the coming years. In particular it was noted that biogeochemical OSSEs must account for the unique characteristics of biogeochemical fields, including strong vertical gradients, sensitivity to biological processes, and dependence on air–sea exchange. They also highlighted the importance of using high resolution models capable of resolving eddy activity, boundary current dynamics, and deep convection. Several speakers suggested that developing these OSSEs will require close collaboration between modellers, observationists, and sensor developers, and could form a cornerstone of future BGC OSSE design.

5.3 Best practices and training

Finally, workshop participants identified a need for shared best practice documents and training in the biogeochemical sphere. While the RAPID and OSNAP communities have developed consistent methodologies for calibrating moored CTDs and processing physical data, similar frameworks for biogeochemical sensors remain fragmented. There was an enthusiasm for community endorsed guidelines covering deployment strategies, calibration procedures, drift correction, data formats, and quality control protocols. Early career researchers (who were well represented at the workshop) were seen as a key constituency for such training. The extensive work already undertaken by the Ocean Observatories Initiative (OOI) was highlighted, where they have developed best practice frameworks for deploying, calibrating, and processing biogeochemical sensors on single fixed open ocean observatories. The progress made within OOI, including sensor specific documentation, standardised calibration workflows, and transparent data quality procedures (Palevsky et al., 2023) was seen as a useful model that could be adapted for AMOC transport arrays. Leveraging this existing knowledge base would accelerate the development of community endorsed guidelines and reduce duplication of effort across programmes, strengthening emerging BGC best practices.

6 Final synthesis and pathways forward

The workshop brought together a diverse stakeholder community of physical oceanographers, biogeochemists, engineers, and data specialists to begin shaping a shared vision for a sustained biogeochemical observing component on AMOC transport mooring arrays.

Taken together, the workshop discussions revealed a new group that is both ambitious and pragmatic about the future of biogeochemical observing within AMOC transport arrays. The technical sessions underscored that while the integration of BGC sensors onto moorings presents engineering, calibration, and data processing challenges, these are substantial but manageable when addressed from the outset. Successful deployments depend on understanding sensor limitations, power consumption, reagents, and drift, and the need to undertake rigorous calibration through high quality discrete samples. Equally important are the engineering adaptations required to integrate new instruments into long standing mooring designs, and the data processing capacity needed to deliver calibrated, traceable BGC records. Experience from RAPID-MOCHA-WBTS, OSNAP, GOHSNAP, OOI, Davis Strait, and Fram Strait demonstrates that BGC sensors can be incorporated reliably when each of the technical, logistical, and data considerations are aligned.

The operational discussions emphasised that working with existing transport arrays requires an appreciation of their logistical constraints, permitting requirements, and tightly choreographed deck operations. These arrays are among the most stable and mature ocean observing infrastructures in the world, and their continuity and established data pipelines make them natural platforms for expanding biogeochemical observing. But successful expansion relies on effective and timely engagement, clear expectations, and an alignment with the capabilities of the array and the teams behind them. Strengthening linkages with complementary systems (including BGC Argo and satellite observing) was seen as a major opportunity for enhancing the value of fixed point measurements and anchoring basin scale biogeochemical products.

Finally, the community priorities discussions pointed toward a shared vision for the coming years:

- dissolved oxygen emerged as the clearest candidate to become a core biogeochemical variable across transport arrays, offering immediate scientific value and a foundation for more complex measurements.
- the development of biogeochemical OSSEs was identified as essential for future array design, so that they can constrain biogeochemical transports with the same confidence as physical ones, and the most efficient use of BGC sensor resources.
- the need for shared best practices, drawing on the substantial progress made within OOI and other programmes, was emphasised as was the importance of training and documentation to support new users and early career researchers.
- the desire to seek future opportunities to come together as a stakeholder community to discuss developments and emerging common issues and challenges.

These priorities reflect a community that is ready to move towards a coordinated, sustained, and scientifically driven approach to biogeochemical observing.

Across all sessions, there was a strong sense that the integration of biogeochemistry into AMOC transport arrays is both timely and achievable, with early examples — from RAPID to GOHSNAP to OSNAP East to Fram Strait — demonstrating what is possible. To realise this vision will require coordination across programmes, investment in sensors and technical and data management capacity, the workshop made clear that the community is aligned on the direction of travel. That of a future Atlantic observing system that is capable of resolving both the physical transports and the biogeochemical fields they carry with unprecedented resolution and accuracy.

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